

Spectrophotometric Study of Ferric—mandelate Complex and its Photoreduction

S. D. Bhardwaj and G. V. Bakore

Mandelic acid (sodium salt) has been found to form a yellow-coloured complex with Fe^{3+} . The complex has the composition $(\text{Mandelate}^-)_2 \text{Fe}^{3+}$ and has maximum absorption at 360 $\text{m}\mu$ between pH 1.0 and 6.0. The values of dissociation constant and ΔF are respectively 1.94×10^{-5} and -436.98 Kcal./mole at 25° .

During photo-reaction of iodine and α -hydroxy-acids in presence of metal ions like Fe^{3+} (Ph.D. thesis, R3j Univ., 1959), it was observed that the complexes of metal ion and α -hydroxy-acids played an important role.

In the present communication the spectrophotometric study of the system mandelate— Fe^{3+} , using various concentrations of the reactants has been made. The composition and the structure of the complex formed have been discussed; the dissociation constant and the free energy of formation of complex have been calculated at 25° .

EXPERIMENTAL

"AnalaR" ferric ammonium sulphate and mandelic acid were used. Other chemicals were also chemically pure. Solutions were made in double-distilled water. pH measurements were made with a Beckman pH meter (Model-H₂). Spectrophotometric measurements were made with a Beckman spectrophotometer (DU Model) with 1 cm cell at $25^\circ \pm 1^\circ$.

Validity of Beer's Law.—From a set of experiments, using different concentrations of Fe^{3+} , it was concluded that the Beer's law was rigidly obeyed between the concentration range of $M \times 10^{-1}$ and $M \times 10^{-5}$.

Nature of the Complex.—In another set of experiments, mixtures containing varying proportions of mandelate and ferric ammonium sulphate (1:1, 1:2, 1:3, 1:4, etc.) were prepared and the optical densities of the solutions at different wave lengths in each case were measured. In all the cases, the maximum absorption occurred at a spectral region of 360 $\text{m}\mu$, thus indicating the formation of only one complex with the reagent (Vosburgh and Cooper, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 437).

Stoichiometry of the Complex.—The composition was determined by Job's method of continued variations (*Compt. rend.*, 1928, **180**, 928). Measurements using equimolecular and non-molecular solutions in large number (total volume 50 c.c.) were made at 360 $\text{m}\mu$. Some of the typical observations are plotted in Fig. 1, where the difference of optical densities of the mixture and Fe^{3+} in absence of the chelating agent is plotted against composition of the mixture. This is necessary because under these conditions ferric iron can also exist as ion pair $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{2+}$ which has maximum absorption in the range of 300-450 $\text{m}\mu$.

The peaks of the curves occur at a ratio of 2:1.

$$\frac{[\text{Mandelate}]}{\{[\text{Fe}^{3+}] + [\text{Mandelate}]\}}$$

FIG. 1. A = $[\text{Mand}] = 10 \times 10^{-3} M$; $[\text{Fe}^{3+}] = 5 \times 10^{-3} M$.

B = " = $[\text{Fe}^{3+}] = 5 \times 10^{-3} M$.

C = " = " = $3.34 \times 10^{-3} M$.

Effect of pH.—Solutions containing the same concentrations of iron and mandelate were prepared at different pH. The pH of the mixture was varied in the range of 1.0 to 6.0. It was found that at all pH's used, the maximum absorption occurred at 360μ , thus indicating that the nature of the complex did not change in the pH range studied.

Sensitivity of the Complex.—Ferric—mandelate complex is stable in diffused room light. In the light from 1000 watt lamp, the complex, however, undergoes photodecomposition. Photodecomposition of the complex takes place in the sunlight as well.

DISCUSSION

Dissociation Constant of the Complex.—For determination of the dissociation constant, we have used the method employed by Mukherji and Dey (*this Journal*, 1957, 34, 461). The difference in optical densities in presence and absence of mandelate is plotted against $(\text{Mandelate}^{-1}) \{[\text{Fe}^{3+}] + [\text{Mandelate}^{-1}]\}$. These plots are shown in Fig. 1. It may be assumed that in descending portion of the curve, when mandelate is in excess, most of the iron is bound in the complex and hence the observed optical density is mainly due to the colour of the complex. We may therefore assume that at points in the curves, where the optical densities are same, the amounts of the complex formed are identical.

In the present case we have:

Taking the two concentrations a_1 and a_2 and b_1 and b_2 for the reactants, giving the same optical density, we have

$$x = \frac{a_1 b_1 - a_2 b_2}{(2b_1 a_1) - (2b_2 a_2)}$$

Knowing the values of x in the above equation, the value of $1/K$, which is the dissociation constant, can be calculated.

We have calculated the values of dissociation constant at optical density 0.300 in the curves A, B and C of Fig. 1 and the average value comes out to be 1.94×10^{-4} (un corrected for ionic strength) at 25°.

The free energy of formation can be obtained from the relation:

$$\Delta F = - RT \ln k$$

where the terms have their usual significance. In this system the value of ΔF at 25° works out to be -36.98 Kcal./mole.

Structure of the Complex.—The ratio of mandelate to iron in the mixture is 2 : 1. The wave lengths at which maximum absorption due to complex takes place does not change with pH in the range of 1.0 to 6.0. Further, the optical density at wave length of maximum absorption remains unaffected by changes in pH in the above range. These facts suggest that the iron-mandelate system can be represented as:

(It may be assumed that the remaining two co-ordination positions are occupied by water molecules).

Photoreduction of the Complex.—The following procedure was used to follow the photoreduction of iron—mandelate complex.

The 1000-watt lamp was run at constant voltage through a variac. Heat radiations were removed by using 0.2M-CuCl₂ solution. The reaction vessel was made of hard glass with parallel faces. The rate of photo-decomposition was studied spectrophotometrically by measuring the optical density at different time intervals. Since Beer's law is valid, the rate at which optical density changes is the measure of the photoreduction. Fig. 2 illustrates the results.

The rate at which the complex undergoes photoreduction follows zero-order law for early stages of the reaction, although towards the end the photoreduction follows first order law.

FIG. 2. Iron-mandelate complex: Photoreduction.
 A=Zero order } [complex] = $30 \times 10^{-2} M$.
 B=First order }

The photoreduction of the complex can be understood on the basis of the following reaction scheme:

[where R is the radical and P is the product of oxidation of mandelic acid. K_e is the fraction of light absorbed by $\text{Fe}[\text{Mandelate}^-]_2$ and I_0 is the intensity of light; K'_e = fraction of light absorbed by FeOH^{2+} ; K_s and K_d stand for the separation of the primary products and dark reaction].

That radical is produced by photo-irradiation of iron-mandelate complex is supported by the work of Levesley and Waters (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 217) on manganese pyrophosphate oxidation of α -hydroxy-acids. On this basis, the rate of photoreduction becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{-d[\text{Fe}^{3+}]}{dt} &= \frac{d[\text{Fe}^{2+}]}{dt} = 2 K_e I_0 + \frac{2 K_s K'_e I_0}{(K_d + K_s)} \\ &= 2 \left(K_e + \frac{K_s K'_e}{K_d + K_s} \right) I_0 \end{aligned}$$

The rate expression shows that the rate is independent of concentration of the complex (i.e., zero order). Since $K_e = (1 - e^{-klc}) > 1$ when concentration is large (c = concentration of the complex; l = path length = 1 cm). When concentration becomes sufficiently less, $K_e > K/c$ and the rate then becomes first order with respect to the complex.

Authors are grateful to Professor S. R. Palit, D.Sc., F.R.I.C., F.N.I., of the Indian Association for Cultivation of Science, for helpful discussion.